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INTRODUCTION

When I came back from working as a remote teacher, which had been my first teaching experience, I experienced lots of the things described in this document. I found behaviour management with urban kids challenging. I doubted myself as a teacher and my competency was doubted by senior staff. I persevered and got through it, largely unsupported. Later as a school psychologist in Darwin I worked with many teachers who went through similar experiences and was able to support them through what I had learned through my experience.

Years later, the Australian Education Union NT branch funded me to carry out a workshop with teachers returning from the bush in Easter that year. The response of the participants was amazing. They described experiencing what is described in this document and wishing they had been exposed to it at the beginning of the year, rather than at Easter. I remember one teacher saying he had just resigned because of his loss of confidence as a teacher due to his experience in the kinds of things described in this document.

As far as I am aware there are still no resources to support teachers and others coming back from the bush. If people are lucky and encounter people who have been through the same thing, they get informal support. If they don't, well they are left to cope best they can. I hope this document can help fill this gap for some, at a time when the COVID pandemic is making support for those who need support harder to find.

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People generally assume that the initial culture shock of going to work in a remote area is the major transition people will experience in going bush. However, returning from the bush can also be a major transition people need to cope with. Returning from working in remote cross-cultural contexts can be as or more challenging than initially going bush. People may experience 'reverse culture shock'. This document was developed originally for the Australian Education Union NT to assist teachers returning from the bush. It has content from work carried out by Christian Fourcard as part of his postgraduate training in Psychology. Later Anne Lord, a school psychologist from Western Australia did some more work on it. Content was added to and edited by me (Dr Damien Howard). I am a psychologist interested in the wellbeing of people working remote – both Non First Nations and Aboriginal.

CHANGED VALUES

Many people leave the remote teaching experience having been changed in significant ways. Close contact with First Nations people and culture can have a profound impact on values and sense of what is important in life. People often describe a greater focus on the importance of people and relationships in their life and a lessening of significance of material possessions.

“I started to get into the swing of life in Perth. You know, renovating the house and stuff and going out for a huge breakfast at a café somewhere and I would feel really guilty and just think, “Is this what’s really important?”

“I was on such a steep learning curve every day, learning about culture and language and I really felt like I was missing out on that learning experience every day when I was in Perth. It was a bit like (the movie) Groundhog Day – I kept waking up hoping that today would be different, exciting and challenging but it was just all the same”.

“I would look at my (non-Aboriginal) nephews and nieces who had so much and never had to struggle for a single thing and would still complain about something. I couldn’t stand their whinging”.
In general teachers report a shift in values as a result of their experiences in remote schools.

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*“I think people who have worked in First Nations communities sometimes have a wider sort of perspective on life...” “I’m realising on a lot of different levels that other people in the world think very very differently. Intellectually, I think we all know that, but until you live with that for a long time it’s very easy to look at differences being worse, “my culture is right and anything different is wrong”, but I think the longer you live with another culture you lose the culture shock and develop greater maturity. **I think life has a lot more areas of grey (now).**”*

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DEALING WITH PARENTS

In First Nations schools, relationships with First Nations parents in the community are often close and important; particularly more so in recent years where community liaison and community support has been a high priority for schools. This involvement often consists of engaging the assistance of First Nations parents in dealing with school issues, particularly behaviour management. While First Nations parents may be involved in school issues it is rare that they are focussed on levels of academic performance on a day-to-day basis. However, many non-First Nations parents are highly concerned about teaching methodology and levels of achievement of their child in class. They will often contact teachers readily and question what they're doing, why they are doing it and how they are doing it.

Many teachers find this an unnerving experience, particularly if their only teaching background had been in remote communities. However, while this is initially challenging in the longer term their experience of developing a collaborative relationship with First Nations parents is an asset to establishing constructive relations with non-First Nations parents. **It is important not to see the questioning of non-First Nations parents as personally challenging, but to see it as a concern for their children's education that needs to be channelled into constructive avenues**, rather than be allowed to progress into an adversarial relationship between teacher and parent.

“Dealing with parents who suddenly appeared on my doorstep at 7.30am in the morning enquiring about their child’s education was something I was not used to. I had to actively seek out parents to discuss their child’s performance in the remote school setting. All of a sudden, I was bombarded with parents wanting to find out about me too. It wasn’t until the end of the year that I found out I was doing “ok”; something I wish they could have told me half way through at least. This was all rather

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difficult to come to terms with. Luckily that support group I had established at my previous school helped me deal with this as they had gone through the same sorts of things”.

“My first parent night was so nerve-wracking, I’m sure I wouldn’t have survived if it hadn’t been for the education assistant in my class. They were asking questions about reading series and specific spelling programs that I hadn’t even heard of. The parents who were teachers themselves were the hardest to deal with – they just sat up the back with their arms folded probably thinking “what does this person know?”

Teachers reported that they noticed a big difference in student relationships and their families, probably an impact of their awareness of First Nations vs Western child rearing practices.

“I really noticed that on-First Nations kids can’t entertain themselves and play like First Nations kids can. It was like they had to be in organised activities all the time. Parents would say kids couldn’t do their homework as “they have swimming at 4.00pm, music lessons at 5.00pm”. I felt a bit like parents lived their lives vicariously through their children”.

SURVIVING THE TRIVIA

After the life and death drama of remote communities, staff room conversations about subjects like home renovations and school uniforms can seem trivial. It can be difficult to participate in a suburban world so removed from the harsher, but what seems more “real” issues of community life. This sense of not being able to relate to seemingly unimportant preoccupations of urban schools is a common reaction of teachers returning from remote schools.

“They (other teachers) would be sitting in the staff room at lunchtime and talking about the latest art house movie they had seen or what they had spent on their housing renovation – it just seemed so irrelevant and meaningless”.

*“I had a parent make an appointment to see me and I was quite nervous and got out portfolios and information about the student’s academic performance. This parent had said they wanted to discuss something quite serious with me and I made an assumption it had to do with their child’s progress. They wanted to talk about their child’s lunch box being taken by another student. **I couldn’t believe it was such a big issue - First Nations kids would have just sorted it out between themselves. I was just oblivious to those sorts of things that non-First Nations parents see as being important”.***

The focus in urban schools on issues of school shoes, uniforms, students being orderly and other aspects of what is seen as superficial discipline is something that can be initially quite difficult.

“I keep seeing teachers tell kids off for not wearing shoes to school. I have to remind myself that that is important here. At my old school things like shoes just weren’t essential – the fact that the kids came to school was really celebrated”.

“As a new administrator to the school I just could not believe that we spent a whole school council meeting and two staff meetings talking about the style of hat that the students would wear. I kept wondering when we were going to talk about really important things like curriculum”.

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ATTITUDES TO INDIGENOUS PEOPLE AND ISSUES

Living and working in remote communities over a number of years gave teachers a deeper insight into First Nations people and their culture. Their experience has given them an understanding and attitude that often contrasts sharply with some of their colleagues. Many ex-remote teachers found it difficult to deal with attitudes of other staff to First Nations students and families.

“I found the attitude of some people to First Nations kids just beyond my depth of perception. It horrified me...and the teachers' attitudes to the parents. It just distressed me beyond belief. I was horrified.”

“I found the ignorance of others with respect to First Nations issues and education really difficult to deal with. And there was this assumption that because I had taught in a remote I would be able to deal with any issue that involved an First Nations student”.

Teachers found covert racism and comments quite difficult to deal with and at times felt somewhat marginalised if they were to speak out. There were also some great opportunities to turn knowledge and understandings into real positive experiences.

“The staff knew that my partner was First Nations and they were very supportive. They asked lots of questions but I think it was a bit of a novelty for some. When the students in my class met my husband I realised that they had all sorts of misconceptions about First Nations people. They had completed some pretty basic First Nations Studies in the previous year and I had to explain to them that no, we didn't eat bush tucker, kangaroo or goanna every night for dinner”.

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"I think having lived in remotes I had a much greater understanding of First Nations culture. I was involved in NAIDOC Week, Sorry Day and First Nations Studies in the urban school that I moved to, and on reflection the skills and abilities I had developed helped the school to make quite significant and genuine moves towards reconciliation."

"My experience working remote has taught me to dig a bit deeper into kids' lives and not just make assumptions about what may or may not be going on for them". "I became a lot more aware of deeper issues of hurt and what might be contributing to problems for students".

BEHAVIOUR MANAGEMENT AND RELATIONSHIPS

Teachers in remote schools quickly learn the importance of building real relationships with First Nations children and the community and not having such a professional distance as with Non Aboriginal students.

"Probably the most important thing about teaching there (in a community) is relating to other people there. ... I think that's the big thing with First Nations people, they see the person rather than a teacher."

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It takes teachers time to learn ways of managing student behaviour that work with First Nations children and the social etiquette in the community. Discipline styles of more successful teachers become less confrontational and based on relationships rather than "respect" for the teacher because of their position.

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Teachers returning to urban schools comment that it is very different, in the first instance, working with non-First Nations children after having taught First Nations children. As teachers reintegrate in their “home” culture may not realise they have very different expectations. Non-First Nations children are often seen by them as self-centred, aggressive and non-co-operative compared to First Nations students.

“Kids aren’t nice to each other at all, they “dob” on each other for the slightest thing and there is such an emphasis on “best friends”. I was used to most of the students in my class being related to one another and although they used to tease each other, generally they were very caring and supportive of their peers”.

Teacher's dissatisfaction often centres around the different styles of behaviour management needed with non-First Nations children. One of the reasons for this is that after establishing a relationship with First Nations students, there is far less need for formal behaviour management strategies. This greatly contrasts with non-First Nations students for whom “crowd control” techniques need to be constantly and vigorously enforced. Rather than seeing this problem as a difference in culture and relationships, teachers often blamed themselves and worried that they would be seen as not being able to manage their class. They were also often ‘blamed’ but senior staff who did not understand the transition.

“I felt like a first year teacher. All the experience that I had, had gone out of the window.”

It is natural that people do what has worked before. However, problems arise when teachers attempt the non confrontational behaviour management strategies that work with First Nations students, with non-First Nations urban children used to the more coercive discipline strategies traditional in schools.

Non-First Nations students are perplexed by the apparent teacher “weakness” and test the boundaries of what they can get away with. Ex-remote teachers strongly acculturated to not using public blaming and overt punishment seek to avoid the boundary setting that students expect of them. The non-compliance and/or defiance of students becomes evident to other teachers and is often seen by them as the teacher having poor classroom control.

“I actually found the urban white kids a lot more difficult to discipline because I didn't know where they were coming from. ... So a lot of the beginning was pure control. A lot of time was spent controlling as opposed to developing rapport”.

“I suppose I'd been so used to living and working with First Nations people, I thought non-First Nations kids were greedy, they were selfish, they didn't think of the other person, they didn't try and get on with people. I just thought, “Oh, God, this is horrible”. I just thought perhaps it was my class and that - it seemed to be all the kids. I've certainly changed my attitude since, but that was my initial attitude. They didn't try and like you or get on with you; they just gave you a hard time all the time. I hadn't struck this before.”

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The fact that urban children were so different to teach came as a surprise to many teachers. The skills they had used in teaching for the last few years didn't seem adequate in this new situation and the skill deficits in non-First Nations students became apparent.

"The kids couldn't do anything independently and it drove me nuts".

"I took a whole lot of kids on camp and quite a lot of them got homesick and wanted to ring up their parents every night and talk to them. That sort of thing never happened when I took remote kids on camp".

Teachers of First Nations students in remote communities learn a range of subtle behaviour management techniques. Not surprising, when teachers move to urban schools with a predominance of non-First Nations children, they find they have been acculturated to avoiding the more confrontational discipline techniques that can be used in urban schools.

Thus, the initial behaviour management problems of many teachers from First Nations schools is not to do with inadequate skills but more to do with highly functional skills of behaviour management of First Nations students not being effective when applied to working with non-First Nations students.

"Yeah, it was initially quite hard because I also went from knowing every student in the school by name to teaching over 120 different students a day in a big high school. The subtle skills I had developed though of not confronting kids actually helped me out a lot when I was given a really difficult class of Year 9 students. The kids weren't actually as different as I thought they might be".

"The students were a different kettle of fish also. I was used to teaching First Nations students who were very tactile, loved touching you and hugs and really wanted to be a part of my everyday life. I had a special bond with them and would see them down the street and when I went out bush, etc. They were always happy to say hello and have a chat. The only time I would see my students from my class now is at the shops with their parents and even then they are too shy to say hello. Their interests are also different. I learnt so much from the First Nations students about their lived, families and culture – I miss that."

The focus on relationships and establishing a positive relationship with students is something that is often retained as a teaching style. Having experienced the importance of relationships as a crucial element of the education equation, ex-remote teachers place a priority on positive social relationships with students and develop them with great success with non-First Nations students.

RECOGNITION OF PROFESSIONAL STRENGTHS AND TEACHER SELF-CONCEPT

Working with First Nations people is one area of expertise fostered by working in remote communities. Experience in remotes also gives teachers the opportunity to become involved in a wider range of professional experiences earlier in their career than most urban teachers. Organising sports carnivals, excursions, charring committees, running the school when the principal was absent, liaising with the community and other agencies and being responsible for cost-centres are all common experiences for teachers in remotes. Teachers returning to urban environments often *find these tasks designated for the more experienced or senior teachers.*

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"I found that being back in a senior high school, I no longer had the big picture of the direction the school was headed in. I was used to being involved in lots of decisions about school and now the only area of impact I have is in my department or with my class".

"I was used to being quite autonomous in my work and feeling like I could make a difference across the district. Now I feel as though everyone has their set roles and tasks – it's more limiting. How can I show people that I can also do x, y and z when I never the chance"?

Some teachers felt that their experiences in remote schools were recognised by others but usually when it came to the area of First Nations Education which had both positive and negative repercussions.

"It was as though I became the resident expert on anything that had to do with First Nations Education. If anything came to the school with the word "Aboriginal" in it, then it went on my desk – it was bizarre".

"I have a number of students in my class with English as a second language and the experiences I have had in teaching ESL have helped me considerably. I found I was also really confident in my lower school maths classes in dealing with such a wide range of ability".

"The range of professional development that I had been exposed to out bush was just outstanding and I have been able to share my knowledge and skills particularly in the area of cooperative learning in my new school."

Teachers in remote locations become used to being recognised by members of the community who identified them as teachers and a person of some status and knowledge. Whilst this could be at times both a help and hindrance, this affirmation of role was often missed in the new location.

"In a remote, I was the principal 24 hours a day, 7 days a week and people would always want to talk with me. When I was living in Perth I could go out to the shopping centre and see nobody I knew which was really strange. I was used to being a "somebody" with a life and a significant role that everyone knew about and all of a sudden I was just a person on the street like everyone else".

"It was really hard for my partner who wasn't working for a while. She had been used to having an important role in a school and people ringing her up and asking questions and valuing her opinion on things. All of a sudden that wasn't happening and it does affect your sense of identity".

Teachers working in remote locations often become very innovative and think "outside the square", often through necessity. The breadth and depth of knowledge is often assumed in others in the new location and teachers and administrators report they were very surprised at the lack of knowledge in particular areas.

"You know things we used to do up there with managing student behaviour – I thought everyone did that sort of stuff. I talked about a few things down south and realised that we were actually quite "cutting edge" in the bush".

Dr Damien Howard
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"I guess you get used to trying lots of things out and taking risks. I think the people in the metro have come to realise that perhaps we aren't the poor cousins after all. I have actually found it really frustrating (the lack of knowledge in others) at times".

STAFF COLLABORATION AND SUPPORT

Teachers found it difficult moving from such a small school with sometimes as few as two colleagues on staff to a large school, with so many different personalities.

"As an administrator I found that instead of making decisions or working through issues with just one or two people, I was faced with 20 different personalities. I had to use mediation and conflict resolution skills a lot more and to consult with so many more people just to get things done."

"I found that I had no idea of the effect moving to a mainstream classroom had on me. I did not recognise the differences between teaching in a remote location and moving to a setting in which I had almost no support from my colleagues. We would sit in the staff room at recess and lunchtime and not discuss the day's happenings. At the remote school I was in, we would laugh about things that happened during the day and commiserate with other teacher about problems they were experiencing and then work through solutions together. I found that staff in town would stay in their cliques and not let others participate in their conversations about their lives outside of school."

Teachers found that collaboration with colleagues on issues became much harder in urban schools as people retreated into their own lives at the end of the day.

"Staff in the remote schools would all stay after school and this was a time to work through issues and concerns they had during the week/day. We were all there for support for each other which extended to our social network too. People in remotes became each others family. In the mainstream school I noticed some teachers would leave as soon as the bell went. It was deserted by 2.30pm."

"Collaboration was something that happened easily in remote schools. Because of the strong relationship between teachers we would grab half an hour here or there when we could, however getting teachers to give up this time proved almost impossible in the town setting. I find that remote schools are a lot more flexible in their timetabling and that we would help each other out; collapse classes, internal relief, etc."

On the other hand, moving to a "town" school has its real positives in the sheer number of teachers in the school.

"I joined a high school where there were 16 teachers in the one department and they became my family and supported me. I had the opportunity to teach in my subject area for the first time at a Year 11/12 level which was professionally and personally rewarding".

"I was quite apprehensive at first going back into teaching in a specific subject area and at a high level, but my Head of Department has been amazing, setting me up with a mentor teacher so I got back into the swing of things quickly. It has been such a supportive environment to be in and they have given me so much time and assistance. There are 11 people in the department – almost as many as the school I came from!"

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FRIENDSHIPS – NEW AND OLD

It was a common experience for ex-remote teachers to feel as though their urban friends could not relate to or weren't particularly interested in their remote experiences. Friendships and the organisation of social activities often seemed to be more difficult and formal in urban centres...

Friendships with other teachers who had been "remote" were close through shared experiences. Working and living in remote communities often creates extremely close friendships that continue after people leave.

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"Developing relationships with others was hard but eventually that has happened through the kids playing junior sport and so on. The formal protocols of friendship are hard to get used to. People just don't drop in or decide to have a BBQ that day".

"As soon as we got here (to our new location) we joined clubs and associations outside of school. Because my wife wasn't working it was really important for her to have that network and it's been fantastic for her. Previously our social group had revolved around school people. Here, everyone leaves as soon as the bell goes - they have their own lives".

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The opportunity to retain these friendships and talk about community issues and current adjustment issues is invaluable. It is important to keep in touch with other ex-remote teachers. Contact with

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them enables you to validate the sense of who you have become through the experience of living and working in remotes. Like any friendships, common past experiences are the basis of mutual acceptance and understanding. This highlights how important remote experience can be in shaping a sense of self.

"I had a really great network of friends who we knew from the bush and they knew what we were going through. I was fairly well prepared in that I knew that this (re-acclimatisation) was a process we would go through and that things would get better".

A TIME OF ADJUSTMENT

How people respond to difficulties of adjustment depends greatly on how they and others perceive them. Seeing the difficulties as part of a normal adjustment process that most people go through helps keep things in perspective.

However, if difficulties are personalised they become more difficult to deal with. If the individual thinks that they as a person is failing in some way then negative, self critical thinking that leads to distress is more likely to result. This is why support by those who understand what people are going through is so helpful to assist in normalising the difficulties experienced. It is also why a critical, blaming response from colleagues and peers which compounds the person's own inaccurate personalising, can be so destructive.

Personalising leads some good teachers to leave teaching, under the mistaken assumption that they are inadequate as teachers. For many others it contributes to a period of low confidence, stress, anxiety and depression.

"To be honest, in Term 1 I was too busy to be aware of what was different. Everything was new and exciting and in an administrative position my feet hit the ground running. By first term holidays I felt things more. I felt like I didn't have a lot in common with others".

"I cried every night for the first five weeks. I actually did know it was going to be difficult and that it would take some time – I still cried though!"

"We decided that it would not be such a good thing to go back (to our old location) for a holiday this year as I knew we would not want to come back (to Perth)".

If you are these experiencing these things seek help. This can come from others who have been through similar experiences or through professional counsellors. If you see a counsellor who is not experienced in working with people who have experienced 'reverse culture shock', give them a copy of this document to read.

THE LITTLE THINGS

Teachers adjust to the relaxed lifestyle that exists in remote schools and the change of pace and often weather brings about unexpected stressors.

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“School was the easy bit – they were so terrific and supportive of me. The lifestyle changes were harder to take. Everything is a much faster pace here – we’re always catching up with people and we have no time to ourselves. Moving to Perth in winter after our leave meant that I couldn’t exercise like I used to which made things worse. Its much better now the weather is warmer”.

“Winter and the rain was a bit of a novelty to tell you the truth”.

“I’ve dreamt of being in Broome when I’m wearing my thermal underwear. Winter is no fun”.

“Things aren’t as relaxed and informal here. People stress out if you just drop in and worry if their house isn’t tidy”.

PERSONAL SURVIVAL STRATEGIES

- ü Seek support from peers who have gone through a similar process. If there are not people in your school it is important to seek them outside the school.
- ü Maintain old networks by writing, phoning and emailing people as much as possible. There is often a period of time when there is a sense of not being understood and feeling that those around you cannot offer what you need. However, these feelings should be relatively short lived. It is important not to give up on people and try to assist them to understand what you're going through.
- ü Keep up your previously existing stress management strategies and incorporate new ones which might be available in your new location.
- ü Don’t personalise the adjustment difficulties you are experiencing by seeing yourself as failing. Rather, consider the differences in school, community and cultural contexts that create differences in skills needed. Problem solve, not personalise.
- ü Seek help to identify what ways things are done differently in urban schools and how you can learn about them. For example, you might ask for a person to act in a peer support role (or you may be lucky enough that your school has allocated one). This person should be someone you are comfortable with and preferably someone who has had some country or remote experience.
- ü Be aware that you are likely to have changed. Your attitudes, beliefs and values may have changed and those of your friends, family and peers has not. Explore these changes without blaming others or yourself.
- ü Inform peers and senior staff about your strengths that can make a contribution to the school community.
- ü Network with others who are or have made the transition from remote to urban school. Keep in touch and be open to their support.

RECOGNISING YOUR ASSETS

Teachers moving from remote communities to urban schools often do not recognise the wealth of knowledge and skills that their experience has given them. It often takes a number of years for this realisation to come.

It is important to be aware what assets your experiences in remote communities have provided.

Add more to the list and refer to it constantly. Your experiences in remote schools have provided you with a wealth of transferable skills (not just applicable to teaching either). Some common assets that teachers develop working in community schools include:

- ü Being more adaptable - able to change at short notice
- ü Skills in ability to work with multi age and multi grade classes

Dr Damien Howard
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- ü Sensitivity to different cultural groups
- ü Priority on developing positive interpersonal relations with students
- ü Diverse school skills eg administration, submission writing, coordinating specialist areas
- ü Ability to relate to a wide variety of groups
- ü Able to work with minimal supervision
- ü Resourcefulness in dealing with problems with minimal support
- ü Ability to improvise
- ü ESL experience
- ü Practical life skills eg. fixing toilets, generators, 4WDs leaking roofs
- ü Appreciation and knowledge of native flora and fauna
- ü Knowledge of First Nations culture and languages

SOME WORDS OF WISDOM

“Coming from the city initially, I thought that integrating myself back into a mainstream society would be easy, however after a while I found I missed “popping” in next door for a coffee and the “open house” nature of living so closely with others. It has taken time to build relationships with others on a professional as well as a social level. I had to actively seek out opportunities where I would meet new people in circumstances where we had something in common. Becoming close to people took a long time.

On the other hand there are so many advantages living in a town close to transport, social activities, sporting facilities and basic facilities that most urban settings have and which most people take for granted. It’s not worse living in a mainstream town, just different.

AI used to create images in this document. Referral to Aboriginal people – usual at the time this was first developed has been changed to First Nation.